

Seed technology

Effect of different doses of gamma rays on germination and survival of upland rice varieties

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Improvement in either a single or a few polygenetically controlled traits is normally not achieved by hybridization within a short time. Alternatively, targeted recombinations through induced mutation can be achieved within a short time without much disturbance of yield and grain quality in well-adapted varieties. This study was conducted to determine the response of eight varieties to different doses of gamma ray with the aim of determining the optimum dose for mutation breeding.

Healthy seeds of uniform size and moisture content of each variety were irradiated at the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay, with gamma ray doses of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 kr. Treated seeds were sown in the field in factorial randomized block design with two replications. Survival percentage was calculated as a percentage of germination based on numbers of plants 15 d after sowing and at harvest. Percentage reduction in germination and survival was calculated over the unirradiated control (see table).

ANOVA indicated varieties did not differ significantly in seed germination (see table) and that dose and dose $\times$ variety effects differed significantly. Percentage plant survival differed significantly among varieties and dose treatments but variety $\times$ dose effect was nonsignificant.

Average seed germination was 74% in unirradiated varieties. Germination

Effect of different doses of gamma rays on varieties for their percent germination, survival, and reduction over control and ANOVA of partitioned sum of squares for gamma ray doses, varieties, and dose $\times$ varieties effect for percentage germination and survival.^a

Gamma ray dose kr/variety	Germination		Survival		
	%	% RG ^b	%	% RS ^c	
<i>Dose</i>					
Control	74.0	-	94.2	-	
10	64.8	12.3	88.3	6.1	
20	65.6	11.3	84.1	10.6	
30	50.1	33.3	91.7	2.5	
40	5.6	92.3	50.1	46.7	
50	3.2	95.1	45.5	51.6	
Mean of doses (Without control)	37.9	48.9	72.0	23.5	
<i>Variety</i>					
Jaya	41.3	42.2	74.5	19.1	
Ghansal	34.2	56.0	66.5	33.4	
JS180	40.7	51.8	45.6	46.7	
Kundlika	35.0	75.0	53.5	44.2	
ACK5	35.0	53.3	92.0	4.9	
R24	34.7	43.2	92.0	1.0	
HS17	41.7	46.7	77.5	17.1	
Basmati	39.0	49.9	72.1	24.2	
Mean	37.7	52.3	71.7	23.8	
<i>ANOVA</i>					
		Germination (%)		Survival (%)	
SV	df	SS	F	MSS	F
Replications	1	230	-	3322	-
Varieties (V)	7	145	0.9 ns	2376	5.8**
Error (a)	7	146	-	406	-
Dose (D)	5	15901	484.7**	7662	16.2**
V $\times$ D	35	69	2.1*	667	1.4 ns
Error (b)	40	32	-	472	-

**, ** = significant and highly significant at P = 0.05 and 0.01, respectively. ns = nonsignificant. ^bRG = reduction in germination. ^cRS = reduction in survival.

decreased from 64.8 to 3.2% as gamma ray doses increased from 10 to 50 kr. Germination percentage at doses of 10-30 kr did not differ significantly, but doses of 40-50 kr resulted in a highly significant reduction in germination (see table).

Lowest germination (34.2%) was observed in Ghansal, followed by R24 (34.7%). Jaya (41.3%) and HS17 (41.7%) were found less sensitive when compared with Ghansal and R24. Highest reduction in germination percentage over respective control was recorded in Kundlika (75%),

followed by Ghansal (56%). Percentage reduction in seedling survival increased from 6.1 to 51.6% as gamma ray doses increased from 10 to 50 kr, except at 30 kr. Seedling survival percentage was highest in ACK5 and R24 (92.0%), although they had low germination percentages. Highest seedling mortality was observed in JS180.

Based on percentages of germination and seedling survival, gamma ray doses of 10, 20, and 30 kr were found to be optimum for mutation breeding in rice. ■